

Why the Disruption index cannot identify the most important literature in the field of Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis?

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Abstract: The Disruption (D) index is a network-oriented metric that measures the extent to which a specific paper disrupts the existing literature. This study aimed to assess the accuracy of the D index by analyzing a sample of literature on Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis (ALS). The findings indicated that the D index did not effectively identify the most significant ALS-related literature. As a result, we suggested that bibliometric indicators encounter challenges in accurately assessing the importance of biomedical literature, particularly in the context of drug research and development, which heavily relies on foundational work in the field and cannot be overlooked in references.

Keywords: Disruption index; Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis; bibliometrics

1. Introduction

It is well-known that the bibliometric indicators play an important role in measuring the progress of scientific work. The Disruption index (D) is one of the significant indicators which measure the paper's importance on either disrupting or developing the current literature (Funk & Owen-Smith, 2017; Wu et al., 2019). Since the D index was first introduced in 2019, it has gained widespread adoption and application by many researchers in different disciplines or fields to measure the network disruption in a short span of time. Numerous studies have applied the D index to identify the most disruptive publications in different disciplines and sub-disciplines, such as surgery (Khusid et al., 2021; Neubauer et al., 2022; Ponsky, 2021; Sullivan et al.,

2021), radiology (Abu-Omar et al., 2022), ophthalmology (Patel et al., 2022), energy security (Jiang & Liu, 2023) and nanoscience (Kong et al., 2023).

The D index is based on citation network which includes three elements: a focal paper, a set of references cited by the focal paper and a set of citing paper of the focal paper and its references. A diagram of the D index calculation is shown in Figure 1. The basic interpretations are that if a focal paper can render its references obsolete, which is indicated by whether the citations of the focal paper do or do not cite the references of the focal paper, then it can be regarded as more likely to be highly disruptive.

Figure 1: Illustration of the Disruption Index.

The convergent and validity of the D index have been widely discussed since it was proposed, which leads to many variants of the index. For example, Bornmann et al. (2020) examined convergent validity of the D index using an external novelty criterion of F1000Prime, a dataset based on post-publication peer review. They found that the original D index may not be effective in identifying the most disruptive publications and hence proposed a modified D_5 index, which excludes all citing papers that cite less than five of the focal paper's references, and it shows the best identifying ability. Chen et al. (2021) criticized that the approach of categorizing technologies as either disruptive or enhancing is incomprehensive. Thus, they introduced a modified tripartite network infrastructure to recognized what they termed "dual technologies".

Additionally, studies have shown that the D index is time-sensitivity, which leads to the requirement for a citation window of at least three years (Bornmann & Tekles, 2019), and it may also work improperly when the focal paper has a large set of highly cited references (Liu et al., 2023; Ruan et al., 2021). Furthermore, Shibayama & Wang (2020) investigated the predictive validity of an index measuring disruption which drops N_k for the reason that it can easily causes possible bias and pushed D scores close to zero (Bornmann & Tekles, 2021), and the results suggested that all variants of the Shibayama-Wang originality perform significantly better at identifying theoretical innovation instead of methodological innovation, but they are all able to predict future citation impact.

Based on Shibayama & Wang (2020)'s research results with data from life sciences, we plan to investigate the applicability of the D index using evidences from ALS-disease related literature, in order to explore whether the D index can efficiently identify the importance of the literature, and then explain the possible reasons.

2. Research design

2.1. Research design

To address the above research question, we share our observations from an exemplary case of amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS). The reason for analyzing articles related to this disease is that ALS is recognized as a rare disorder , occurring in only 1.5 to 3 per 100,000 people annually in North American and European populations, with only four approved drugs (see Table 1) since 1983 (Kraft et al., 2023). Thus, it is easier to localize all milestone papers related to the FDA approved drugs. The milestone papers are referred to as the most importance papers in the current study.

Table 1. FDA approved drugs related to ALS since 1983

Drug	Designated year	Approved year
Riluzole(Rilutek)	1993	1995
Edaravone(Ridicava)	2015	2017

Sodium phenylbutyrate and taurursodiol (Relyvrio)	2017	2022
Tofersen(Qalsody*)	2016	2023

For each drug, We broadly divide the process of new drug R&D into six stages: disease, disease-gene, gene, gene-drug, drug, drug-disease, which nearly covers all the elements of the entire process of new drug development (Bártfai & Lees, 2005; Petrova, 2014). We construct our dataset using different specialized biochemical and pharmaceutical databases, then we choose the most important discoveries based on certain criteria within each stage. By comparing changes in the D value of these publications, we examine the structure of the citation network, to evaluate the applicability of the D index in identifying the most important ALS related literature.

2.2. Data sources and manipulation

Data are collected from several biochemical and pharmaceutical databases, i.e., Orphanet, PubMed, MalaCards and PubChem. For each paper, we used three different citation windows to check the robustness of the results. The citation windows used in each case were D_3 (a three-year citation window), D_4 (a four-year citation window), and D_5 (a five-year citation window). We formed the dataset based on certain strategies shown in the following Table 2. After cleaning the data manually, we get a total of 28,880 articles.

Table 2. literature retrieval strategy

Section	Dataset	Strategy
Disease	PubMed	retrieval formula is (((((amyotrophic lateral sclerosis[Title]) OR (ALS[Title])) OR (charcot disease[Title])) OR (lou gehrig disease[Title]))) OR (amyotrophic lateral sclerosis[MeSH Major Topic])
Disease-gene	MalaCards	Every directly related article in publications sector
Gene	MalaCards	Every article referenced by elite genes
Gene-drug	PubChem	Every article provided in chemical-gene co-occurrences in literature sector

Drug	PubChem	Every article provided in consolidated references sector
Drug-disease	PubChem	Every article provided in chemical-disease co-occurrences in literature sector

It should be noted that the synonyms of ALS are obtained from Orphanet and the literature retrieval was with a restricted time parameter till March 2024. And articles from publications sector in MalaCards were chosen to represent the section of disease-gene are because they come from curated sources (ClinVar, OMIM®, GeneReviews, MedlinePlus, miR2Disease, GARD, Novoseek, and PubMed) and are associate with the disease-related genes. MalaCards contains detailed information (<https://www.malacards.org/>). Furthermore, literature associated with drugs was specifically limited to the four medications shown in Table 1, but for the reason that sodium phenylbutyrate and taurursodiol(Relyvrio) and Tofersen(Qalsody*) are not a discrete structure, articles represented the latter three sections are absent.

Based on the dataset we constructed, we further identify **the most disruptive** articles in each stage. Selection criteria are mainly based on publication date. Articles with the earliest publication dates in each stage were regarded as the most innovative articles, however, some details may be adjusted depending on the reference databases of different stages. Articles represent disease-gene section was chosen not entirely based on publication date for MalaCards has already ranked the articles first according to the number of sources that associate the article with the disease-related genes, then by date of publication and we followed this sorting principle. For the similar reason, articles represent gene section is the first publications of the elite gene with the highest gene-disease association score in every disease in the Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis family. Articles represents gene-drug and drug-disease sections, on the other hand, is selected first based on the correspondence with elite genes and diseases and then by date of publication. Finally, we calculate the D values using PubMed and get a total of 21,213 articles.

3. Results

3.1. Descriptive statistics

Figure 2 shows the distribution of all the articles in our dataset. It is clear that most articles, regardless of the stage of the drug R&D, can be defined as developing work with negative D values and over 99% literature has a D value within the (-0.1,0.1) interval.

Figure 2. Kernel density distribution of the D values calculated based on PubMed in a three-year citation window.

However, we chose 6 articles with the highest D values ($D_3=1$) and found that the majority come from disease stage with only one article stemming from drug stage. Details of the six papers are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Six Papers with $D_3=1$.

Articles	I_3	J_3	K_3	D_3	D_4	D_5
(Moore, 1993)	1	0	0	1	1	0.75000
(Towse & Pritchard, 2002)	3	0	0	1	1	1
(Das et al., 2012)	19	0	0	1	1	0.96429
(Singh et al., 2018)	5	0	0	1	1	1

(Kutlubaev et al., 2023)	1	0	0	1	1	1
(Rolland et al., 2021)	1	0	0	1	1	1

The six papers share a common feature: their lower j and k values in the formula are caused by a lack of references, and lead to high D values. The decrease of D values in the five years citation window for (Moore, 1993) and (Das et al., 2012) is also due to a slight increase of k . Subsequently, upon investigating the six articles, we found that none of them can be considered as disruptive work, as they did not make significant contributions to the etiology or treatment of ALS either at theoretical or practical level. We selected a group of articles deemed as groundbreaking works in each stage according to Table 2. The reason why we use publication date as the criterion is that the earliest published literature in a field has a higher probability of pioneering or making relatively new discoveries.

It should be noted that some articles are excluded because they are not on the definitional domain of the D index. We sorted these articles, as the top ten are shown in Table 4. Similarly, we found that none of their D values have outstanding performance. Compared to the six papers with $D_3=1$, their lower D values may be caused by the high value of k , indicating a large amount of references the focal papers cited. Specifically, we explored the citation relations of these articles and found that they cited numerous highly cited review literature. Existing studies demonstrated that k can easily lead to bias, especially in life science (Shibayama & Wang, 2020). Based on the observations, we infer that the D index may not work efficiently in biomedicine as they prefer a more comprehensive citation habit, leading to the high value of k .

Table 4. The top 10 papers with the highest D_3 values

Articles	I_3	J_3	K_3	D_3	Rank
(Smith et al., 2017)	53	40	17980	0.00072	1753
(Mizoule et al., 1985)	5	1	25259	0.00016	2257
(Sheerin et al., 2014)	1	1	110	0	2383
(Carr, 2015)	0	0	47	0	2383
(Tunca et al., 2020)	2	6	29856	-0.00013	4582

(Liu et al., 2022)	0	1	6803	-0.00015	4641
(Takahashi et al., 2013)	11	15	14966	-0.00027	5178
(Kume et al., 2023)	0	1	2316	-0.00043	5996
(Course et al., 2020)	5	25	28262	-0.00071	7198
(Brenner et al., 2018)	16	70	48088	-0.00112	8791

3.2. Comparisons of the D index

We compared the D values of the representative articles with the rest in each stage as shown in Figure 3. The representative articles of the disease section are excluded for the same reason mentioned above. For the rest stages, it is evident that none of these papers has a notably high D value within its stage.

Figure 3. Boxplot of the distribution of the D values for each stage. The representative articles are marked with yellow circles.

3.3. Citation relationships

The above case study of ALS illustrates that the D index did not identify the most important ALS literature as expected. In response, we offer a speculation: the process of new drug R&D is a mature chain linking science and industry that each stage of the study builds upon fundamental research. Consequently, the D index identifies few disruptive articles in the field. We posit that studies of disease-related genes will cite

articles on early diagnosis of the disease, while articles focus on lead compounds will cite articles centered on disease and genes, and finally papers directly related to drug development will cite key papers from all the above stages, which means research of every stage heavily relies on foundational work in the field and cannot be overlooked in references.

To test the above speculation, we chose (Bensimon et al., 1994) to be the focal paper as it demonstrates that riluzole, one of the FDA approved drug for ALS, can slow the progression of ALS and is regarded as a representative article in drug-disease stage. Subsequently, we explore its citation lines. A conceptual diagram is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. A conceptual diagram of the citation lines. Each circle represents a division. From left to right are Disease, Disease-gene, Gene, Gene-drug, Drug and Drug-disease. In our dataset, (Bensimon et al., 1994) was classified under drug-disease stage and it cited (Rothstein et al., 1992) which is in disease-gene division, and multiple articles, such as (Caroscio et al., 1987), (Plaitakis et al., 1988) and (Testa et al., 1989) in disease division. In the same time, (Plaitakis et al., 1988) and (Testa et al., 1989) are both references to (Rothstein et al., 1992), indicating an approximately linear citation relationship.

4. Discussion and conclusions

In this study, we used ALS related papers as examples to reveal the insights underlying

the effectiveness of the D index as applied to the biomedical field. The results of the study show that most papers in biomedicine, especially in a disease related field, whether conceptual or applied do not disrupt its predecessors.

Organizational innovation process can be differentiated by radical and incremental innovation (Ettlie et al., 1984). In the context of drug R&D, the model of combining theoretical research with industrial transformation makes it difficult to measure the disruption of articles by a fixed standard or indicator. By using the D index for measurement, we propose the hypothesis that despite the presence of disruptive outcomes, the process of new drug R&D, from target discovery to clinical trials, is difficult to measure by indicator based on citation network, for its papers representing important innovations are also stand on the shoulders of previous research thus cannot overshadow or disrupt its predecessors, whether in the same domain.

The study's contribution lies in enhancing our understanding of the applicability of the D index and proposing a challenging question: how should the importance of biomedical literature be measured.

Despite the contributions of this study, there are some limitations. First, this study only analyzed ALS-related papers to discover new insights about the D index. Due to the rarity of ALS, the results may not be generalizable to other areas in biomedicine. Second, the assessment of the judgment on the whole process of drug R&D is mainly based on literature review as the authors lacked professional expertise in the field. Consequently, there may be inherent biases or omissions in the dataset. In future work, we plan to expand our dataset to validate the findings. Additionally, we will consider using MeSH terms to categorize articles into different domains, and segmenting the drug R&D process into specific disciplines for more detailed comparisons and citation network explorations.

Open science practices

All sampled articles in our dataset were retrieved from public databases which are PubMed, PubChem and MalaCards. Detailed retrieval formula is presented in the paper. The data that support the findings of this study are now openly available in GitHub

(https://github.com/Alexnjusim/ALS_dataset.git). We processed the data with Python and the source codes to calculate the D value are available on request from the corresponding author.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jingyi Xu: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Data curation, Writing - original draft. Yizhe Yuanzhang: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Data curation. Xin Liu: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing. Jiang Li: Supervision, Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing–original draft, Writing–review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that would influence the results reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. D values of the representative articles

Fid	PMID	D₃	D₄	D₅
1	19312323			
2	19979321			
3	19983800			
4	19986696			
5	19986785			
6	19989197			
7	21611266			
8	29009806			
9	29584061			
10	29822142			
11	28469040	0.000719	0.000355	-0.00019
12	24562058	0	-0.01481	-0.01258
13	32579787	-0.00013	-0.00013	-0.00013
14	36204986	-0.00015	-0.00015	-0.00015
15	24119685	-0.00027	-0.00025	-0.00012
16	37339631	-0.00043	-0.00043	-0.00043
17	32750315	-0.00071	-0.00071	-0.00071
18	29342275	-0.00112	-0.00111	-0.00101
19	11951178	-0.00194	-0.00268	-0.00253
20	27455347	-0.00219	-0.00256	-0.00245
21	19344878	-0.00358	-0.00268	-0.00165
22	30348461	-0.00383	-0.00482	-0.00482
23	30879340	-0.0055	-0.0084	-0.0084
24	23771029	-0.0062	-0.00737	-0.00826

25	22801503	-0.01112	-0.0114	-0.01251
26	12858291	-0.01195	-0.01257	-0.01315
27	26556829	-0.01356	-0.01308	-0.01414
28	21842496	-0.02131	-0.02525	-0.02758
29	20110243	-0.02429	-0.02491	-0.02688
30	19118816	-0.02521	-0.03065	-0.02862
31	20577002	-0.0281	-0.02608	-0.02544
32	23455423	-0.05506	-0.05385	-0.05524
33	15106121	-0.10026	-0.10543	-0.11418
34	25374358			
35	28469040	0.000719	0.000355	-0.00019
36	1259395	0	0.033898	0.046875
37	24119685	-0.00027	-0.00025	-0.00012
38	29342275	-0.00112	-0.00111	-0.00101
39	9837826	-0.002	-0.00265	-0.00344
40	31332380	-0.00241	-0.00254	-0.00254
41	22801503	-0.01112	-0.0114	-0.01251
42	12840784	-0.01117	-0.01058	-0.01101
43	23454272	-0.02308	-0.02041	-0.01704
44	26945885	-0.025	-0.02861	-0.02696
45	19118816	-0.02521	-0.03065	-0.02862
46	14770181	-0.02639	-0.02698	-0.02887
47	21857683	-0.0398	-0.04336	-0.04401
48	15372378	-0.0502	-0.06179	-0.06437
49	23455423	-0.05506	-0.05385	-0.05524
50	11834836	-0.06048	-0.05388	-0.05428
51	17322883	-0.06395	-0.05543	-0.04991
52	16501576	-0.08264	-0.05332	-0.03188
53	2328408			

54	14887941			
55	25374358			
56	16899637	-0.00234	-0.00271	-0.00274
57	19593125	-0.00261	-0.00172	-0.00192
58	8967745	-0.02469	-0.02531	-0.023
59	20942785			
60	3018617	0.000158	0.000193	0.000245
61	14887941			
62	8302347	-0.00864	-0.00623	-0.00711
63	17127563	-0.01148	-0.00999	-0.01338